
**Exploring the Feeding Habits of Chanda Nama in Borgaon Reservoir,
Yavatmal, Maharashtra**

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Abstract:

In the Yavatmal region, Borgaon Reservoir is well-known for its ability to produce fish. Fishery department has given on lease basis to local fishermen societies. Carp species seeds were introduced for economical benefits. In the current study, the feeding habits of Chanda Nama in the Borgaon Reservoir in Maharashtra's Yavatmal district are examined. Chanda nama is also known as the elongate Glassy Perchlet, Because of its transparent body, which is utilized as an aquarium fish and internationally it is called as the elongated glassfish. This species is important to the aquatic ecosystem, and the study aims to understand its feeding habits and dietary preferences. Field observations, stomach content analysis, and laboratory tests were used to gather data between April 2023 and March 2024. The outcomes show that the main food sources for Chanda nama are zooplankton (65%), aquatic insects (45%), algae (25%), and detritus (9%). Seasonal changes were noted, with insects predominating in the summer and zooplankton consumption rising during the monsoon. This research provides insights into the ecological role of Chanda nama in freshwater ecosystems and highlights the importance of conserving its habitat.

Keywords: *Chanda Nama, Feeding Habits, Borgaon Reservoir, Yavatmal, Maharashtra, Freshwater Ecology.*

Introduction:

The primary source of energy is food, thus choosing fish species that coexist with other fish and make use of all the resources in the water bodies without competition is crucial. To comprehend fish growth, breeding, and migration, a thorough study of their food and feeding behaviors is necessary. (Sengbira K Sangma, 2019). The diet and feeding habits of fish are important in the selection of fish for culture because they help the fish dwell in groups that maximize the amount of food available and reduce competition for food. (Prakash, 2020)

Environmental conditions, prey abundance, and habitat availability are some

of the elements that affect feeding patterns. Research on feeding ecology and food preferences is essential to comprehending fish roles in their environments because it shows interactions based on eating resources and indirectly reveals community energy flux, which enables the inference of the impacts of predation and competition on community structure. (Bhuvanewari. R1, 2018)

The Borgaon Reservoir, a well-known water body in Yavatmal, Maharashtra, is known for its rich biodiversity and for supporting a wide variety of aquatic life, including the fish Chanda nama. The elongate glassy perchlet

(Chanda nama) is a species of freshwater fish in the Asiatic glassfish family Ambassidae, the only species in the genus Chanda. Internationally it is also known as the elongated glassfish. It is native to an area of south Asia from Pakistan to Burma, in the Indomalayan realm. The longest total length of the elongated glassy perchlet is 11 cm. Their bodies are compressed, deep, and short. The snout is pointed, and the head is likewise small and compressed. In particular, the mouth is broad and curved upward. Compared to the upper jaw, the lower jaw is longer. Lips are thin. In some species, villiform teeth can be found on the palate and tongue in addition to the jaws. (Bhuvanewari. R1, 2018)

According to earlier research, Chanda nama is a carnivore that mostly consumes debris, zooplankton, and tiny invertebrates. However, its feeding habits in certain habitats, such as the Borgaon Reservoir, have not been studied. The purpose of this study is to look at the feeding behaviors of Chanda nama in this reservoir by analyzing its foraging techniques, diet composition, and how environmental factors affect its feeding habits.

It is crucial to comprehend Chanda nama's feeding habits in order to evaluate both its ecological importance and the condition of the aquatic ecosystem in which it lives. The Borgaon Reservoir is a perfect place to research these feeding patterns because of its varied aquatic vegetation and wildlife. By knowing Chanda nama's dietary

choices, we can better manage and conserve freshwater environments and gain insight into its place in the aquatic food web.

Through this study, we intend to fill the knowledge gap about the ecological function of Chanda nama in Borgaon Reservoir and offer useful data for conservation efforts. Our research of this species' feeding patterns will improve our biology knowledge while also advancing our understanding of Maharashtra's freshwater ecosystem dynamics. Furthermore, these data can be used to evaluate how human activity affects the biodiversity and water quality in the area.

Material and Method:

Study Area:

This study was carried out in the Borgaon Reservoir in Yavatmal, which is situated approximately 11 km to the east-northeast of Yavatmal city (20.452929 N, 78.190815 E), close to Madani Town in the outskirts of Yavatmal. It is built on top of the nearby Nallah River and impounds it. Irrigation is the dam's main function. The dam is 830 meters (2723.1 feet) long and 20 meters (65.6168 feet) high above the lowest foundation. It has a volume content of 0.01404 kilometers (0.00337 cubic miles) and a gross storage capacity of 0.01404 meters (0.003368 cubic miles). Yavatmal, in the Yavatmal District of Maharashtra, is the city nearest to the dam. The Borgaon dam is commonly referred to as "Borgaon Lake or Borgaon Talav" in popular culture.

Figure 1. Photograph of Borgaon Reservoir of Yavatmal district.

Collection of Specimens:

From April 2023 to March 2024, near about 65 Chanda nama specimens were collected from the Borgaon reservoir. For the study, three sites were chosen. A cast net was used to catch them, and the specimens were subsequently transported in an ice box to the lab. To remove extra water from the specimens' bodies, they were mopped on filter paper.

Methodology:

After collecting fish samples, their stomachs were thoroughly dissected, the

weight of the gut was recorded using an electronic balance, the contents were examined and identified under a light microscope, and the various foods were identified and measured. The percentage of each food item was noted and examined using the percentage of occurrence method (Pillai, 1951). The contents of the stomach were lastly preserved in 10% formalin. The observations of gut contents were divided into various groups, including Zooplankton, Aquatic insects, Algae, Detritus.

Figure 2. Photograph of Chanda nama Fish.

Figure 3. Photograph of Dissected Chanda nama Fish.

Figure 4. Photographs showing zooplankton, insect, and algae in the gut content of Chanda nama.

Results and Discussion:

The Borgaon Reservoir, a well-known waterbody in Yavatmal, Maharashtra, is known for its abundant biodiversity and for supporting a diverse range of aquatic species, including the fish Chanda nama. The study of the feeding habits of the elongate Glassy Perchlet, or Chanda nama (Hamilton, 1822), provided important information about its food preferences in the Borgaon Reservoir. Over a 12-month period, from April 2023 to March 2024, approximately 65 specimens were collected for investigation of the stomach content. Laboratory research, stomach content analysis, and field observations were used to evaluate the fish's diet.

According to the findings, the primary food sources for Chanda nama consisted of zooplankton (65%), aquatic insects (45%), algae (25%), and detritus (9%). The species is an opportunistic feeder that can make use of the resources in its surroundings, as seen by its varied diet. The large proportion of zooplankton in the diet

indicates that Chanda nama is essential for regulating zooplankton populations, which maintains the aquatic ecosystem's general equilibrium. It also represents the availability of this food source in the reservoir. According to the study, the Chanda nama's food habits also showed significant seasonal fluctuations, Aquatic insects were discovered to be the main food source during the summer, however zooplankton consumption increased significantly during the monsoon season. Environmental changes in the reservoir and variations in food availability are the causes of this seasonal shift in diet.

This study provides important new information about the food preferences and feeding patterns of Chanda nama in Borgaon Reservoir. The results highlight the species' function as an opportunistic feeder with important ecological implications. It is essential to understand these processes in order to develop conservation measures that effectively safeguard Chanda nama and its habitat against environmental changes.

Figure 5. Pie chart showing Percentage of Gut content.

Conclusion:

In the Borgaon Reservoir in Yavatmal, Maharashtra, the feeding habits of Chanda nama (Hamilton, 1822), also referred to as the elongate Glassy Perchlet, have been studied. This research provided significant knowledge about the dietary preferences and ecological role of this species. Over a 12-month period, thorough

field observations, stomach content analysis revealed that Chanda nama generally consumes zooplankton (65%), aquatic insects (45%), algae (25%), and detritus (9%). The results demonstrate a distinct seasonal variation in feeding patterns, with a large increase in zooplankton intake during the monsoon season and a notable increase in aquatic insect consumption throughout the

summer. This diet adaptability highlights Chanda nama's function as an opportunistic feeder, able to react to the fluctuating availability of food sources in its surroundings.

The ecological significance of Chanda nama goes beyond its dietary habits; as a consumer of both zooplankton and aquatic insects, it plays a pivotal role in maintaining the ecological balance within the Borgaon Reservoir. The findings of this study underscore the ecological significance of Chanda nama as both a consumer and a contributor to the health of the freshwater ecosystem. By controlling zooplankton populations and acting as prey for larger fish species, Chanda nama plays a vital role to maintain the ecological balance within the Borgaon Reservoir. In conclusion, understanding Chanda nama eating behaviors is essential for developing conservation plans that protect its habitat and guarantee the long-term viability of aquatic biodiversity. In order to better understand the ecological dynamics of this species and its interactions within the aquatic ecosystem, more investigation and observation are recommended.

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